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Research Article

ASSESSMENT OF LOGISTICS MANAGEMENT PERFORMANCE FOR KEY ESSENTIAL MEDICINE IN PUBLIC HEALTH FACILITIES OF AWI ZONE, AMHARA REGIONAL STATE, NORTH WEST ETHIOPIA

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Abstract

Background: Poor performance of pharmaceutical logistics management not only wastes a resource, but also hampers availability and access to essential medicines in poorest countries of Africa and Asia, where more than 50% of their populations lack access to essential medicine for their primary health care needs.

The aim of this study was to assess the logistic management performance for key essential medicine in public health facilities of Awi zone, Amhara region, North West Ethiopia.

Methods: A facility based cross sectional study was conducted from March 15, 2019 – May 15, 2019 in 22 selected public health facilities in Awi zone. Quantitative data was collected by using semi-structured questionnaire and check list adopted from logistics indicator assessment tool. Qualitative data was collected by physical observation and in-depth interview of key informants was carried out by using tools adopted from logistics system assessment tool. The collected data were entered and analyzed by using Statistical package for Social Science version 23 for windows. Descriptive findings were presented by tables and charts. Fisher's exact test was conducted to determine certain characteristics of the health facilities that are significantly associated with availability of essential medicines.

Result: A total of 22 health facilities were included in this study. All health facilities surveyed in this study used bin card for logistic data recording but the majority, 20(90.9%), did not use stock card for logistic data recording. Fourteen of the health facilities used electronic stock tracking system as a logistic data recording tool. The 16(72.7%), 18(81.8%) and 14(63.6%) of the health facilities have storage, integrated pharmaceuticals and logistics management system and quantification guide lines respectively. The mean absolute percentage forecast error was 41.42%. And average percentage availability of key essential medicines on the day of visit was 85.6%; the majority, 20 (91%) of surveyed facilities practice consumption method to quantify their pharmaceutical demand and 17 (77%) of health facilities used bin card as a source of data for quantifying their essential medicines demand. The 19(86%) of the health facilities have developed their own specific drug list and used it as a reference tool for procurement; regular supportive supervision and use of electronic stock tracking system to record logistic data was found to be significantly associated with availability of essential medicines ($p < 0.05$). The 18(82%) of facilities did not full fill the criteria: products should be stacked at least 30 cm away from the walls and the current space and the organization should be sufficient for existing products and reasonable expansion.

Conclusion: The essential medicines selection performance of the facilities included in this study in terms of preparing facility specific drug list and its utilization was good. Forecasting performance of facilities in terms determining their annual essential drugs demand was poor. Majority of facilities have inadequate space and lack safe storage condition.

Key words: logistics management, performance, key essential medicines, public health facilities; stock out

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1.INTRODUCTION:

Health services provision depends on the availability of essential medicines (1). Essential medicines not only save lives and prevent epidemics and diseases but also promote trust and community participation in the health care system too (2, 3).

Logistics management is the part of supply chain management (SCM) that plans, implements, and controls the efficient and effective forward and reverse flow and storage of goods, services, finances and related information between the point of origin and the point of consumption in order to meet customers' requirement (4). Logistics management includes selection, quantification, procurement, storage, inventory management, distribution, use and data collection and reporting. A successful logistics system ensures availability of essential medicine in the right quantity, in the right condition, at the right time and at the right cost (5, 6).

Pharmaceutical expenditures in developing countries account between 10-40% of public health budgets. In Africa it ranges from 24% in South Africa to 66% in Mali (7). Lack of careful selection, incorrect quantification, high prices, improper storage, expiration of medicines, irrational prescribing, corruption, and incorrect medicine use by patients cause total losses of 70 percent of the above original expenditure (3).

Poor performance of pharmaceutical logistics management not only wastes a resource, but also hampers availability and access to essential medicines in poorest countries of Africa and Asia, where more than 50% of their populations lack access to essential medicine for their primary health care needs (8). Poor availability of essential medicine especially in public sector where majority of poor peoples relies on, results in increased burden of preventable disease, loss of productivity, socio economic and political consequence as well as loss of

confidence and community participation in the health care system. Many of these sources of wastage could be reduced if basic principles of medicine management and use are followed. An efficient and robust logistic management in public health facilities ensures rational selection, quantification, procurement, storage, distribution, use and thereby availability of the right drugs in the right quantities, at reasonable prices, and at recognized standards of quality throughout the year without any stock-out periods is ensured (9).

In the health sector, no health care system can afford to supply all drugs that are available on the market. Selection of medicines ensures that available financial resources are used wisely to provide a limited list of drugs and dosage forms that are appropriate to the health problems of a country or community (3). But studies conducted in different countries showed that there exist malpractices regarding product selection and procurement. The study conducted in Nepal showed that majority of the visited facilities had no facility specific drug list and medicine procurement was done based on doctors' prescriptions (prescriber's preference) which is heavily influenced by pharmaceutical companies' marketing strategies. The study further revealed that majority of visited facilities used an expensive direct procurement model for purchasing medicines (10). Again in a study conducted in Tanzania, only 38 % of surveyed public health facilities have their own essential medicine list. Among these only 52% of facilities procured medicines within essential drug list (EDL) (11).

The ultimate goal of health logistics system is availing the right product, at the right quantity, at the right quality, in the right cost to the right place at the right time. Despite this fact studies showed that public health facilities experienced frequent stock out of essential medicines everywhere (2). A study conducted in Uganda public health facilities revealed

that key essential medicines was stock out for average of 5 months (12).

African countries in particular Sub-Saharan countries faced several challenges regarding pharmaceutical logistics management like lack of information communication technology, adequate storage facilities, management commitment, transparent procurement procedures, guidelines for good storage procedures, appropriate planning, monitoring and

2. METHODOLOGY:

Study area and period

The study was conducted in selected public health facilities of Awi zone, Amhara regional state, North West Ethiopia. Awi zone is one of 12 zones found in Amhara regional state, which is located 452 km away from Addis Ababa, the capital city of Ethiopia. The health service is provided by total of 254 public health facilities; including five hospitals, one general hospital and four district hospitals, 46 health centers and 203 health posts, and 190 private health facilities (114 clinics, 71 drug stores, 4 rural drug vendors and one medium diagnostic laboratory center). This study was conducted from March 15, 2019 to May 15, 2019.

Study design

A facility based cross-sectional study was used to explore logistic management system performance for key essential medicines in public health facilities found in Awi zone, Amhara region, North West Ethiopia.

Sample size determination

The rapid pharmaceutical management assessment (RPMA) guideline developed by management science for health (MSH) (1995), recommends at least 20 health facilities should be used to evaluate the logistics management performance of the facilities in a given area (14). Then 10 percent of the calculated sample size was added for non-respondents and finally sample of 22 health facilities was included in the study. Regarding to the products studied, all 22 budget key essential drugs taken from zonal tracer drug list of hospitals and health centers developed by zonal health department to treat top ten diseases was used. And eight key informants (four pharmacy unit heads, two logistics officers, one hospital medical director and one health center head) were participated for in-depth interview.

evaluation and adequate budget allocation (13). Despite this fact logistic management performance of key essential medicines in public health facilities found in Awi zone is yet not assessed. Therefore this study assessed and measured the logistics management performance for key essential medicines and associated challenges in public health facilities in Awi zone, Amhara region, North West Ethiopia.

Data collection method

Data collection instrument

A semi structured questionnaire and observational check lists adopted from logistics indicator assessment tool (LIAT) which was developed by the USAID-funded DELIVER PROJECT, Task order 1, to assess health commodity logistics system performance and commodity availability at health facilities was used to collect quantitative data(14, 15).

Data collection procedure

The quantitative data was collected by trained data collectors from the recorded documents of twenty two revolving drug fund tracer drugs (i.e. 22 annual quantification documents, 22 annual physical inventory records, 22 expired drug registry book, 22 receiving and issuing vouchers and 446 bin cards) were reviewed. And physical observation of twenty two medical stores and physical inventory of 446 RDF tracer drugs were conducted. In depth interview of 8 key informants (one hospital medical director, one health center head, four pharmacy unit head and two logistics officers) was conducted by principal investigator (PI).

Data quality control

Before data collection, the data collection tool was checked for completeness, accuracy, clarity and consistency by the investigator and necessary modification was made timely. The pre-test was done before actual data collection on one health facility; which was not included in the study to ensure the validity of the collected data. The data collection process was supervised and the completed questionnaires were reviewed by principal investigator (PI) to clarify any data inconsistencies.

Data processing

The quantitative data were checked for completeness and then annual consumption of each tracer drug, mean absolute percentage error, average stock out duration, inventory accuracy rate, percentage of facilities which fulfill the acceptable medicine storage condition, the amount and value of tracer drugs wasted due to expiration were calculated.

Ethical clearance

Before commencing data collection ethical clearance & approval letter was obtained from institutional review board (IRB) of Jimma University and was submitted to Amhara regional health bureau and then the permission letter was obtained. The researcher has given full information on the purpose and objectives of the study to the study participants in order to empower the study participants to make informed decisions on whether to participate or not.

Operational Definitions

Availability key essential medicine: The presence of at least a single unit of usable/ unexpired stock on hand in the facility store or dispensary at the day of visit.

Facility specific drug list: A document which contains a list of drugs, supplies and laboratory reagents approved for use in a given facilities.

Good forecast: Forecasts with forecast accuracy error (MAPE) $\leq 25\%$.

Physical inventory: A manual counting of usable drugs available in store.

RDF drugs: Drugs purchased by the facilities own budget

3. RESULT:**3.1. Demographic data**

This study was conducted on 22 health facilities (5 hospitals and 17 health centers) and 44 (22 pharmacy unit heads and 22 store managers) respondents. All store managers participated in this study have education level of diploma. The majority, 18(82%), have work experience of 1 year- 5 years.

With respect to training received, the 19(86%) are trained for integrated pharmaceuticals and logistics management system (IPLS) and none of the study participants have received drug quantification training (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of pharmacy unit heads and store managers in selected public health facilities of Awi zone, Amhara region, May 2019.

Variables		Store manager Freq. (%)	Pharmacy head Freq. (%)	Total
Educational qualification				
	Diploma	22 (100%)	19(86%)	41(93%)
	Degree	0	3(14%)	3 (7%)
Service year (experience)				
	6 month- 1 year	4(18%)	0	4(9%)
	1 year- 5 year	18(82%)	6(27%)	24(55%)
	Above 5 years	0	16(73%)	16(36%)
Types of training taken				
IPLS*	Trained	19(86%)	22(100%)	41(93%)
	Not trained	3(14%)	0	3(7%)
DTC*	Trained	0	6(27%)	6(14%)
	Not trained	22 (100%)	16(73%)	38(86%)
Quantification	Trained	0	2(9%)	2(5%)
	Not trained	22(100%)	20(91%)	42(95%)

IPLS*: Integrated pharmaceuticals and logistics management system

DTC*: Drug and therapeutics committee

3.2. Availability of logistics data recording tools and guidelines

All the health facilities included in this study used bin card for logistic data recording but the majority, 20(90.9%), of the health facilities, do not use stock card for logistic data recording. Fourteen of the

health facilities used electronic stock tracking system (HCMIS) as a logistic data recording tool. The 16(72.7%), 18(81.8%) and 14(63.6%) of the health facilities have storage, integrated pharmaceuticals and logistics management system (IPLS) and quantification guide lines respectively (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Availability of logistics data recording tools and guidelines in selected public health facilities of Awi zone, Amhara region, May 2019.

Variable	Frequency (%)	Total
Bin card	Yes =22(100%) No= 0	22
Stock card	Yes =2 (9.1%) No = 20(90.9%)	22
HCMIS[electronic stock tracking system]	Yes =14(63.6%) No = 8(36.4%)	22
Guidelines	Storage guide line	Yes= 16(72.7%) No = 6 (26.3%)
	IPLS*	Yes = 18(81.8%) No = 4(18.2%)
	Quantification guide line	Yes =14(63.6%) No = 8(36.4%)
Supervision for data recording	Procurement guide line	Yes =16 (72.7%) No = 6 (26.3%)
		Yes = 18(81.8%) No = 4(18.2%)

IPLS *: integrated pharmaceuticals and logistics management system

3.3. Availability of essential medicines list in the health facilities

Selection of the medicines used at each facility level is the primary job of logistic management department. So this study measured proportion of health facilities that developed facility specific drug

list and proportion of facilities that used this document as reference document for selecting drugs for procurement. As shown below in (**Fig.1**), the 19 (86%) of facilities have developed their own specific drug list and used it as a reference list for procurement of medicines.

Figure 1: Availability of facilities specific drug list in selected public health facilities of Awi zone, Amhara region, May 2019 (N=22).

3.4. Quantification performance

Quantification performance of a given health program is measured by a standard indicator as forecast accuracy error. The majority, 20 (91%), of surveyed facilities used consumption method to quantify their pharmaceutical demand and 17 (77%) of health facilities (HFs) used bin card as a source of data for quantifying their essential medicines demand. And only 2(9%) and 5(23%) of the health

facilities used morbidity status and model 22 as source of data for demand forecasting for forecasting their essential medicine demand. The forecast error of each product line by line was measured by mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and found to be 41.42%, which is beyond the acceptable margin of error and the absolute percentage error ranges from 3.8% for ciprofloxacin to 85.5% for Ampicillin injection (**Table 3**).

Table 3: Forecast accuracy error for RDF key essential medicines in selected public health facilities of Awji zone, Amhara region, May 2019.

SN.	Name of tracer drug	Unit	Forecasted demand	Consumption adjusted for stock-out days	Absolute deviation	Absolute Percentage Error(APE)
1	Amoxicillin syrup	Bottle	11,607	26,781	15,174	56.7%
2	Amoxicillin capsule	Box	2,904	4,345	1,441	33.16%
3	Ceftriaxone injection	Vial	58,309	151,065	92,756	61.4%
4	Metronidazole injection	Vial	25,120	55,894	30,774	55%
5	Ciprofloxacin tablet	Pk.	9,962	10,363	401	3.8%
6	Doxycycline capsule	Pk.	3,963	9,256	5,293	57.1%
7	Metronidazole capsule	Box	1,074	1,249	175	14%
8	Metronidazole syrup	Bottle	3,071	3,800	729	19.18%
9	Cotrimoxazole syrup	Bottle	10,041	16,885	6,844	40.5%
10	Antacid suspension	Bottle	5,095	10,965	5,870	53.5%
11	Tetracycline 1%	Tube	14,516	25,252	10,736	42.5%
12	Paracetamol tablet	Box	924	1,324	400	30.2%
13	Paracetamol syrup	Bottle	21,745	12,566	9,179	73%
14	TAT injection	Amp	16,518	24,789	8,271	33.36%
15	Mebendazole tablet	Pk.	295	472	177	37.5%
16	Oral rehydration salt	Sachet	69,502	64,047	5,455	8.5%
17	Ampicillin injection	Vial	11,598	80,264	68,666	85.5%
18	Gentamycin injection	Amp	21,226	16,630	4,596	27.63%
19	Chloroquine tablet	Box	317	242	75	30.9%
20	Benzoic acid 6% + salicylic acid 3% skin ointment	Tube	11,713	18,923	7,210	38.1%
21	Hydralazine injection	Amp	15,620	25,640	10,020	39%
22	Fefol tablet	Box	9,812	33,586	23,774	70.78%

$$\text{Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE)} = \frac{\text{sum of APE}}{\text{number of items}} = 41.42\%$$

RDF*: Revolving drug fund

3.5. Wastage rate of RDF key essential medicines

Wastage rate is one of the indicators used to measure inventory management performance of health facilities. It is computed by dividing the amount or value of products wasted due to expiry / damage/loss to the total amount or value of the same product throughout the year. The total value of studied essential medicines available in the 2010 EFY(2018 GC) was **13,249,073 ETB** and the total value of essential medicines wasted on the same year was **49,092.14 ETB** in 22 surveyed facilities (**Table 4**).

3.6. Availability and stock out rate of RDF key essential medicines

For health facility to function adequately, essential medicines should be available throughout the year. The availability and stock out of essential medicines was assessed by observing the presence of the each product in the shelf on the day of visit and the stock out duration of the last 12 months was determined by assessing the bin card transaction report i.e. by counting the number of days between zero quantities on hand and until the essential medicine is received. The average availability of RDF key essential

medicines per item on the day of visit was 85.6%. Almost all, 21(95%), of tracer drugs were stock out on the last 12 months. The mean stock duration ranges from 0 days for chloroquine to 44.86 days for

metronidazole injection and average days of stock out duration of key essential medicines were 15.56 days and stock out rate was 4.28% (**Table 5**)

Table 4: Wastage rate of key essential medicines in EFY 2010(2018GC) in selected public HFs of Awi zone, Amhara region, May, 2019(N=22).

List of key essential medicines	Unit	Total quantity (Beg. Balance + quantity 2018 GC)	Price(ETB*)	Quantity Expired in 2018GC	Price of drugs Expired (ETB.)
Amoxicillin syrup	Bottle	23,773	391,065.85	0	0.00
Amoxicillin 500 mg capsule	Box	4,321	1,728,400	0	0.00
Ceftriaxone 1 gram injection	Vial	144,236	3,459,264	0	0.00
Metronidazole injection	Vial	49,025	686,350	0	0.00
Ciprofloxacin 500 mg tablet	Pack.	10,155	812,400	34	2,788
Doxycycline 100 mg capsule	Pack.	9,209	755,138	6	492
Metronidazole capsule	Box	1,232	184,800	0	0.00
Metronidazole syrup	Bottle	3,621	39,831	0	0.00
Cotrimoxazole syrup	Bottle	16,408	171,463.60	152	1,659.8
Antacid suspension	Bottle	9,975	139,650	0	0.00
Tetracycline 1% eye ointment	Tube	24,438	78,201.60	400	2,400
Paracetamol 500 mg tablet	Box	1,307	130,700	0	0.00
Paracetamol syrup	Bottle	11,493	80,451	400	2,800
(TAT) Injection	Ampoule	22,915	1,185,622	120	6,208.8
Mebendazole 100 mg tablet	Pk.	466	16,776	30	1,080
Oral rehydration salt(ORS)	Sachet	63,329	221,651.50	500	1,750
Ampicillin injection	Vial	78,813	173,388.60	0	0.00
Gentamycin injection	Ampoule	16,425	65,700	4,866	19,464
Chloroquine tablet	Box	242	72,600	16	9,540
Benzoic acid +salicylic acid	Tube	17,200	184,040	85	909.50
Hydralazine injection	Ampoule	23,140	671,060	0	0.00
Fefol tablet	Box	33,348	2,000,520	0	0.00
Total amount and value		565,071	13,249,073	6,609	49,092.14

$$\text{Wastage rate by value} = \frac{\text{Total value of expird tracer drugs in EFY 2010}}{\text{Total value of tracer drugs in EFY 2010 (begining+recived)}} \times 100 = 0.37\%$$

$$\text{Wastage rate by amount} = \frac{\text{Total amount of tracer drugs wasted in EFY 2010}}{\text{Total amount of tracer drugs in EFY 2010}} \times 100 = 1.17\%$$

ETB*: Ethiopian birr

Table 5: Availability and stock out duration of key essential medicines in the public health facilities of Awi zone, Amhara region, May 2019 (N=22).

SN.	List of tracer drugs	Available in the day of visit		Duration of stock out in the last 12 months	
		Yes Freq. (%)	No Freq. (%)	Total days of stock out (n=22)	Mean stock out duration
1	Amoxicillin 250 mg/ 5 ml syrup	14 (64%)	8 (36%)	903	41.04545
2	Amoxicillin 500 mg capsule	22 (100%)	0 (0%)	38	1.727273
3	Ceftriaxone 1 gram injection	16 (73%)	6 (27%)	363	16.5
4	Metronidazole injection	7 (32%)	15 (68%)	987	44.86
5	Ciprofloxacin 500 mg tablet	22 (100%)	0 (0%)	161	7.318182
6	Doxycycline 100 mg capsule	21 (95%)	1 (5%)	41	1.863636
7	Metronidazole 250 mg capsule	21 (95%)	1 (5%)	90	4.090909
8	Metronidazole syrup	21 (95%)	1 (5%)	378	17.18182
9	Cotrimoxazole syrup	20 (91%)	2 (9%)	227	10.31818
10	Antacid suspension	15 (68%)	7 (32%)	725	32.95455
11	Tetracycline 1% eye ointment	20(91%)	2 (9%)	259	11.77273
12	Paracetamol 500 mg tablet	22 (100%)	0(0%)	105	4.772727
13	Paracetamol syrup	19 (86%)	3 (14%)	686	31.18182
14	Tetanus antitoxin (TAT) inj.	16 (73%)	6 (27%)	607	27.59091
15	Mebendazole 100 mg tablet	22 (100%)	0 (0%)	100	4.545455
16	Oral rehydration salt(ORS)	21 (95%)	1 (5%)	90	4.090909
17	Ampicillin powder for injection	21 (95%)	1 (5%)	146	6.636364
18	Gentamycin injection	20 (91%)	2 (9%)	99	4.5
19	Chloroquine tablet	22 (100%)	0 (0%)	0	0
20	White filed skin ointment	17(77%)	5(23%)	731	33.22727
21	Hydralazine injection	14 (67%)	8(33%)	783	35.59091
22	Ferrous sulphate +folic acid tablet	21 (95%)	1 (5%)	57	2.590909
Average availability on the day of visit		414(85.6%)	70(14.4%)	-	-

Total days of stock out for all tracer drugs in last 12 months = 7,576

$$\text{Stock out rate} = \frac{\text{Total number of stock out days for all tracer drugs}}{\text{Total number of tracer drugs (22 x22) x 365}} \times 100 = 4.28\%$$

3.7. Storage conditions of key essential medicines

As provided on the table 7, all facilities full filled the five storage criteria for drugs; products should be arranged in a way that identification labels and expiry dates and/or manufacturing dates are visible, products should be stored and organized in a manner accessible for first-to-expire, first-out (FEFO) counting, products should be stacked at least 10 cm off the floor and products storage area should be secured with a lock and products should be stacked not more than 2.5 meters. The 18(82%) of facilities did not full fill the following two criteria; products

should be stacked at least 30 cm away from the walls and the current space and the organization should be sufficient for existing health facilities(**Table 6**).

3.8. Challenges to logistic management of essential medicines by the health facilities

Inappropriate use of medicines wastes resources and hence seriously undermines the quality of pharmaceutical care provided to patients. Selecting the right medicine of the right quality in right quantity is the only solution to deliver quality pharmaceutical care to the patient. Skill gap, lack of training for drug and therapeutics committee (DTC), poor data quality, market inflation, lack of sufficient

space, safety and storage equipment and human resource constraint were mentioned by key

informants as a challenge for logistic management of essential medicines in the health facilities.

Table 6: Adherence to principles of good storage conditions in selected public health facilities of Awi zone, Amhara region, May 2019 (N =22).

SN.	Description	Criteria fulfilled		
		Yes Freq. (%)	No Freq. (%)	Tot.
1	Products are arranged so that identification labels and expiry dates and/or manufacturing dates are visible.	22 (100%)	0 (0%)	22
2	Products are stored and organized in a manner accessible for first-to-expire, first-out (FEFO) counting and general management.	22 (100%)	0(0%)	22
3	Cartons and products are in good condition, not crushed due to mishandling.	20 (91%)	2 (9%)	22
4	The facility makes it a practice to separate damaged and/or expired products from usable products and removes them from inventory.	20 (91%)	2 (9%)	22
5	Products are protected from direct sunlight.	21 (95%)	1 (5%)	22
6	Products are protected from water and Humidity.	20 (91%)	2 (9%)	22
7	Storage area is visually free from harmful insects and rodents.	20 (91%)	2 (9%)	22
8	Storage area is secured with a lock and key, but is accessible during normal working hours; access is limited to authorized personnel.	22 (100%)	0	22
9	Products are stored at the appropriate temperature according to product temperature specifications.	18 (82%)	4 (18%)	22
10	Roof is maintained in good condition to avoid sunlight and water penetration.	20 (91%)	2 (9%)	22
11	Storeroom is maintained in good condition (clean, all trash removed, sturdy shelves, organized boxes).	17(77.3%)	5 (22.7%)	22
12	The current space and organization is sufficient for existing products and reasonable expansion.	4 (18%)	18 (82%)	22
13	Fire safety equipment is available and accessible	12 (55%)	10 (45%)	22
14	Products are stored separately from insecticides and chemicals.	8 (36%)	14 (64%)	22
15	Products are stacked at least 10 cm off the floor.	22 (100%)	0	22
17	Products are stacked no more than 2.5 meters high.	22 (100%)	0	22

3.9. Factors significantly associated with availability of essential medicines

The association of regular supportive supervision and use of electronic stock tracking system to record logistic data with availability of essential medicines was assessed using fisher's exact test. Accordingly,

regular supportive supervision and use of electronic stock tracking system to record logistic data was found to be significantly associated with availability of essential medicines ($p<0.05$)(Table 7).

Table 7: Association of selected characteristics of the health facilities with availability of essential medicines, Awi zone, Amhara region, May 2019.

Variable		Response/ outcome variable		Fisher's Exact test	
		% availability of tracer drug on the day of visit		Df	P - value
		Good (>80%)	Poor (<80%)		
Regular Supportive supervision	Received	13 (72.2%)	5 (28.2%)	1	0.017
	Not received	0 (0%)	4 (100%)		
Using HCMIS	Yes	11 (78.6%)	3 (21.4%)	1	0.026
	No	2 (25%)	6 (75%)		

4.DISCUSSION:

Pharmaceutical logistics management is a key functional area for success of any health care program. Its ultimate goal is to fulfill the six rights (the right medicine, in the right quantity, in the right quality, at the right price, at the right time and to the right place/ person) to satisfy patients.

This study revealed that 19(86%) surveyed facilities have developed their own specific essential medicines list and used it as a reference document to select medicines for procurement. The proportion of facilities that has developed their own medicine list is significantly higher than the result of a study conducted in Tanzania where only 38 % surveyed facilities had their own medicine list (11) and South Africa where essential drug list were not available in the surveyed facilities (16). Again this finding is better than the study conducted in public health facilities in southern part of Ethiopia where none of the visited facilities have developed their own specific drug list (17). The difference may be due to the presence of drug and therapeutic committee that is responsible for preparing facility specific drug list in this study.

Quantification performance of a given health program is measured by a standard indicator i.e. forecast accuracy error. Forecast is rarely perfect, and the error results in deleterious impact and increases the organizations cost by up to 30% which causes substantial burden to the system performance (18). In the current study the majority, 20(91%), of health facilities used consumption method of quantification while the rest, 2(9%), of health facilities used both morbidity and consumption method of quantification in combination. This finding is better than the study conducted in public health facilities of Uganda where health facilities used neither morbidity nor

consumption methods of quantification to estimate their essential medicine demand and requisitions were based on credit available (19). The difference may be due to the availability of drug and therapeutics committee (DTC) and quantification committee in the present study. The current study further assessed forecast accuracy error of facilities by measuring mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and found to be 41.42%, which is significantly higher than a standard margin of error for good pharmaceutical forecast which is $\leq 25\%$ (18).

The current study calculated the wastage rate of essential medicines due to expiry. The result showed that the wastage rate was 0.37%, which is lower than the study conducted in Nepal (20) and East Shewa zone of Ethiopia (21) where the proportion of products wasted was 8.4% and 10.43%. The difference may be due to difference in practicing first expiry first out (FEFO) principle.

Availability of key essential medicines in the health care setting is an indicator of well-functioning logistics system. In order to improve the logistics management system performance, the system should be evaluated regularly by using standard indicators (6). The present study revealed that average availability of key essential medicines on the day of visit was 85.6%, which is better than the study conducted in India (15), Swaziland (22), Uganda (19), and South Africa (18) where mean availability of medicines were 41.3%, 68%, 79.53%, and 80% respectively. On the other hand, the result of the current study is lower than the study result of a study conducted in Malaysia (24) and Nepal (20) where average availability of medicines were 95.4% and 92.44%. The variation may be due to difference in the number of facilities and products studied.

Heat, light, moisture and pest cause damage to medicines (25). Medicines have to be protected from theft, expiration, and physical damage and fire. The quality of storage setting of essential medicines setting is key issue and time-to-time assessment of the storage condition of the drugs is advocated (24). This study assessed the storage condition of key essential medicines and find out that 45% of the facilities stores fulfilled the minimum standard set by good storage guide line for pharmaceuticals.. And the finding of this study is higher than the result of the study conducted in Uganda public health facilities (12) and East shewa zone of Ethiopia (21) where only 10% and 25% of facilities respectively fulfilled the good pharmaceutical storage condition criteria. The difference may be due to availability of storage guide line and pharmacy professionals managing the warehouse in the current study. The present study result is lower than the result reported from a research conducted in Tanzania where 52% facility warehouses fulfilled the minimum standard (26). The difference may be due to lack of management commitment to full fill storage equipment as mentioned by key informants *"...our store room is not sufficient and equipment's like refrigerator, shelves and fire safety equipment are not fulfilled. I have reported this several times to the facility management but no response. I think the management did not understand the characteristics of pharmaceuticals to such extent."*

Pharmaceutical logistic management in low and middle income countries face several challenges as lack of systematic, coordinated approaches to key functions concerning pharmaceutical supply management, poor and/or absence of communication between stakeholders, limited availability of quality data regarding utilization of key essential medicines in the facilities prevents adequate forecasting of demand and appropriate quantification of the medicines essential to meet requirements at a regional, district and community level (6, 27). This study identified that lack of training to the drug and therapeutics committee (DTC), budget constrain, inadequate human resource, poor data keeping and poor infrastructure/ resource as the main challenges of the logistic management of essential medicines in the surveyed facilities. The finding of this study is in line with the study conducted in Sub-Sahara countries where poor infrastructure, poorly trained staff on logistics management and insufficient budget allocation are main challenge for logistics management (13).

CONCLUSION:

The essential medicines selection performance of the facilities included in this study in terms of preparing facility specific drug list and its utilization was good. Forecasting performance of facilities in terms determining their annual essential medicines demand was poor. Majority of facilities have inadequate space and lack safe storage condition.

Limitation of the study

This study did not address some components of the logistics cycle such as serving the customers or patient use because it needs another approach other than used in this study.

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Declarations

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Author's contribution: Author AT involved in the conception and design of the study, participated in the literature searches, supervised data collection and analyzed data. Author GT participated in the design of the study, supervised data collection and the overall research, and commented the manuscript. Author TS involved in the conception and design of the study, participated in the literature searches, analyzed data and wrote the manuscript. All the authors approved the final manuscript.

Availability of data and materials: The supporting documents for this study can be available from the corresponding author upon request.

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